

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842
ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue VI, June 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala

PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 0000000000

DTI Business Reg. No. 30344

TIN 293-150-678 / Business Permits

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2500

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

*"Write. Connect.
Educate."*

@pinagpalapublishing

pinagpala_publishing

www.pinagpalapublishing.com

A Teacher's Summer Dream

CHARAGIN A. GUADALQUIBER

Teacher III

*Calolot Elementary School
Zamboanga del Sur, Region IX, Philippines*

A month of peace, a month of rest,
A teacher's time to feel their best.
No lessons plan, no papers to grade,
Just sunny days in the cool shade.

A break from chalk, from books, and boards,
Time to explore and forge new chords.
With family close and friends so near,
A time to laugh, a time to cheer.

The ocean waves, the mountains high,
New places seen with a joyful sigh.
Hobbies picked up, dreams pursued,
In this special time, spirits renewed.

Children's laughter, stories shared,
Moments of love, a heart prepared.
For when they return to the school once more,
They'll be ready to teach, inspire, and soar.

So, here's to the break, so well deserved,
For the teachers who give and never swerve.
A 30-day rest, a gift so sweet,
A time to make their own hearts beat.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.12590485

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.